

Analyse the electrification pathways for Nigeria to Achieve Universal Access by 2040

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Executive Summary

Key Findings

Higher Demand

- Overall Electrification in 2040: 100%
- Total Investment Cost: 49.14 billion USD
- New Connections in 2040 from 2022: 38.59 million
- Mini-grid connections for each Urban and Rural Area: 1:9
- Total Capacity added from 2022-2040: 34469.57 MW

Lower Demand

- Overall Electrification in 2040: 100%
- Total Investment Cost: 4.41 billion USD
- Additional people in 2040 from 2022: 38.59 million
- Mini-grid connections for each Urban and Rural Area: 1:9
- Total Capacity added from 2030-2040: 5771.42 MW

Recommendation

- The electricity public and private institutions in Nigeria should make real-data used in the utility to ensure a better understanding and findings
- Promote regional collaborations and strategic grid intensification within ranges

Introduction

Project Scope

Nigeria, home to over 220 million people (Sasu, 2024), significant power outage issues due to the disparity between electricity demand and the country's generation capacity. As industrialization outpaces our ability to electrify the nation, the power sector and economy are undergoing transformative changes. According to recent policy outlined in 2021 (Sustainable Energy for All , 2023) through the documented Nigerian Energy Transition Plan (Nigeria Energy Transition Pathways, 2022) the goal under SDG7 is to achieve universal access to electricity by 2030. However, this target appears somewhat unrealistic¹, as electrification accessibility in Nigeria was only about 60.5% as of 2022, with a disparity between urban areas at 89% and rural areas at 27% (World Bank, 2023). Therefore, this report adopts a more realistic timeline, aiming to achieve universal electricity access by 2040. To address this objective, a GeoSpatial Modelling toolkit, 'OnSSET²,' was employed using key assumptions, dividing the study into two scenarios: Higher Electricity Demand and Lower Electricity Demand.

OnSSET is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based optimization tool that is used to support electrification planning and decision making with the aim of achieving energy access goals in unserved locations.

Project Objectives

- Analyse the electrification pathways for Nigeria to Achieve Universal Access by 2040

The main objectives helps in answering these research questions: (OnSSET, 2016)

- What type of technology would be used at each time split to achieve universal access to electricity by 2040
- How is the technology split on each settlement over the period of study
- What is the least-cost technology for each settlement
- What is the required investment to achieve universal electrification at each time split

¹ George-Ikoli, T. and Molineris, M. (2024) *Power to the people: Perspectives on nigeria's energy transition plan*, Natural Resource Governance Institute. Available at: <https://resourcegovernance.org/articles/power-people-perspectives-nigerias-energy-transition-plan> (Accessed: 22 August 2024).

² OnSSET also known as Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool

Methodology

This study made use of OnSSET, a GIS based model to support the electrification planning of Nigeria by identifying least-cost technology that could be deployed in unserved areas while estimating the investment needs. The process consists of collecting input data, setting parameters, model calibration, and electrification investment scenarios to explore pathways leading to the achievement of electrification targets. The data source is divided into GIS model and non-GIS model.

GIS Raster Format

GIS Vector Format

Key Assumptions and Scenario Analysis

Higher Demand

- Mini-grid Interconnection
- Urban tier 5 and Rural tier 3
- Annual max_newgridconnection_limit = ∞

Lower Demand

- No Mini-grid Interconnection
- Urban tier 3 and Rural tier 1
- Annual max_newgridconnection_limit = ∞

Result Analysis

Question 1:

- *What type of technology would be used at each time split to achieve universal access to electricity by each time split*

Figure 1: Electrification Accessibility based on Technology Split in Base Year

Scenario 1:- U5T and R3T

Figure 2: Higher Demand Scenario based on Technology Split in 2040

Figure 3: Higher Demand Scenario based on Technology Split in 2040

Question 2:

- How is the technology split on each settlement over the study period

Figure 4: Higher Demand Scenario based on Technology Split for each settlement in 2030

Figure 5: Lower Demand Scenario based on Technology Split for each settlement in 2030

Question 3 and 4:

- *What is the least-cost technology for each settlement*
- *What is the required investment to achieve universal electrification at each time split*

Figure 6: Higher Demand Scenario based on LCOE and Investment Cost for each settlement in 2030

Figure 7: Lower Demand Scenario based on LCOE and Investment Cost for each settlement in 2030

Discussions

This study is based on the Nigerian Electricity Act, 2023, which allows Nigerian states to generate and transmit power within their boundaries to enhance electricity affordability and achieve sustainable electric power. Analysing the base-case year from 2022, it is evident that most of the electricity generated comes from the existing grid and PV mini-grids. As shown in Figure 1, the electricity demand does not meet the supply, as indicated by the significant percentage of grey areas.

To achieve the study's goal of bridging Nigeria's electricity gap to 100% by 2040, the OnSSET toolkit selected the least-cost technologies based on variables such as electricity demand, population, existing and planned infrastructure, and other factors. Consequently, the results show that higher demand scenarios necessitate a greater reliance on PV mini-grids and grid extensions, whereas lower demand scenarios tend to favour standalone PV systems. Figure 3 illustrates that in the lower demand scenario, the southern part of Nigeria, which is more industrialized than other regions, relies more on the existing grid rather than stand alone PV systems.

Regarding investment costs and the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for each settlement, it is observed that clusters with higher populations, such as Lagos State, incur higher investment costs compared to settlements in rural areas. Furthermore, when comparing the two different scenarios, the higher demand scenario results in higher investment costs and LCOE due to the increased energy generation and greater use of existing grid infrastructure and grid extensions, which are more cost-effective than deploying standalone PV systems.

In terms of policy recommendations, the decentralization of energy generation systems for settlements can be feasible. In the Scenario with high energy demand, more settlements are connected to the grid or are electrified by using PV-Mini grids. Whereas, in the low energy demand, electrification is done mainly by using stand-alone PV solutions. Scenario 1 will represent a total investment of USD \$49.4 billion while scenario 2 requires USD \$4.41 billion. Scenario 1 relies more on grid expansion, which will need to increase the installed capacity of Nigeria from 34.5 GW to 5.27 GW in 2040 to achieve the target of electrification.

Conclusion

This research highlights the potential and challenges of achieving 100% electricity access in Nigeria by 2040 under the framework of the Nigerian Electricity Act, 2023. The study finds that while decentralization of power generation, through technologies like PV mini-grids and standalone PV systems, offers a viable pathway to meeting local energy needs, the effectiveness of these solutions varies significantly depending on regional demand, existing infrastructure and investment cost.

Higher demand scenarios favour the expansion of the existing grid and the deployment of PV mini-grids, which prove to be more cost-effective due to economies of scale and reduced levelized costs of electricity (LCOE). In contrast, lower demand areas, particularly in less industrialized regions, may need to rely more on standalone PV systems, though these come with higher costs.

The findings also show the importance of strategic planning and regional collaboration. States with limited energy resources may not achieve self-sufficiency through internal generation alone. Therefore, inter-state electricity trade and the optimization of grid extensions are critical to ensuring equitable and sustainable electricity access across Nigeria.

Ultimately, this study concludes that while the decentralization approach is promising, it requires careful consideration of regional differences, demand forecasts, and the potential for energy trading to effectively close the electricity gap by 2040.

Recommendation

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